

A Simplified Approach for the betterment of Linearity in a 10-bits Segmented Current Steering DAC

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Abstract:

An analog signal is a route and base of any type of communication. Our universe is full up of analog signals which later converted to digital form for many uses [1]. To make a successful communication process between DSP chips and power amplifiers, the role of digital to analog converter (DAC) is very important and it acts like a path between them. Data converters are always playing like a channel for the communication process as the communication system is based on the bandwidth value [2]. This paper describes the construction, design, principle of operation, and the needs of a specially designed current steering DAC (Segmented format) having resolution of 10-bit and can produce a better linear output than the currently existed DAC. The main concept behind its construction is to maintain the balance between chip area consumption and accuracy with the help of a suitable current source. This sketched-form of DAC can be done with the help of a popular and demanded software Cadence Virtuoso (Version: - IC-615) which the product of National Semiconductor, USA using 180 nm technology. The 10-bit DAC is divided into 2 parts, each having 5-bits. The 5 MSB bits can be implemented by using a unary DAC and the rest 5 LSB bits can be implemented by using a binary DAC [6]. The former DAC is used to increase the linearity in the output and the latter is used for reduction in the implementation area of the chips which can be achieved with the compromising in linearity. But with some special care, and manipulation in design, proper linear output can be attained even after decreasing the chip designing area [18].

Keywords: Cadence, Linearity, Binary DAC, Current Source, Unary DAC, Matching, Band Gap References, Decoder,

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the drastic growth of the communication system, the demand for a single chip, high resolution, high speed and low power consuming Digital to analog converters (DACs) are increased. So to produce an optimized DAC at a cheap price the segmented current steering DAC is highly preferable. Current steering DAC architecture is proposed for high bandwidth converters. It generally performs by adding the current delivered by an array of current sources in various fashion. A load resistor is used to produce a voltage which is connected across the current source [3]. When the current source releases the current and it passes through the load resistor, it produces voltage. Then the output voltage is obtained from the voltage division between the voltage drop across the load resistor and the power supply connected to the load resistor. As an op-amp is not necessary for the production of output voltage, a higher performance of converter can be achieved. The current steering DAC is used to get high bandwidth. More than 12 bits have been implemented using this architecture. Still implementing the high resolution makes the converter more difficult to achieve high speed. So to maintain the balance between resolution and

bandwidth 10-bit design was preferred. Basically, a current steering DAC can be implemented by using a binary-weighted current source, unary weighted current source, and segmented current source [4]. In the current steering DAC, the current sources are summed in a different way to get the accurate current value. Fig.1 illustrates a unary current steering DAC. This type of configuration requires an array of current sources, which is having a unit current value I , each. When all the provided digital inputs are zero and no current sources producing I_{OUT} , instead of one index position the MSB that is D_{2^N-2} is equivalent to two index positions. For example, for the implementation of a 5-bit converter, 31 current sources labeled from D_0 to D_{30} will be required. An example of a radio frequency transceiver system is shown in Fig. 1. The antenna receives the audio signal amplified by a low noise amplifier. Then the ADC converts the low noise amplified signal to digital form and that digital signal is processed in DSP block. After processing, that digital signal converted to analog form through an N bit DAC. N represents the number of bits which is the same as N of ADC. Then that converted signal amplified by a power amplifier and transferred by the antenna.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of an RF transceiver

Now the fact is that the electronics areas like computers, electronics, embedded and instrumentation systems like camcorders, mobile phones, HDTVs, etc. need for the DACs with high feature requirements. The requirements consist of features like high accuracy, linearity, low power, high speed, reliability, and so on.

2. ARCHITECTURE OF SUGGESTED CURRENT STEERING DAC

The complete block diagram of suggested DAC Architecture is shown in Fig. 2 [9-11]. This fig illustrates those five significant bits i.e. B0 to B4 are considered as LSB and they are used to regulate the 5 inputs of the sub-binary converter. The sub-binary DAC is designed by five binary-weighted current sources having a weightage of 1, 2, 4, 8, and 16 multiplied with "I". Here "I" is the unit weight of least current cell and the value for "I" is considered as $5 \mu\text{A}$. Similarly the other five significant bits i.e. B5 to B9 are considered as MSB and they are used to convert binary codes to thermometric codes and these thermometric decoded outputs regulate MSB current matrix. The 5-bit unary DAC is a composition of 31 unit current cells. The size of the MSB current matrix is 4×8 from which 31 cells are used and the 32nd cell is considered as dummy cell. The matrix is realized in the shape of a rectangle and each of the cells has a weightage of $32I$. To realize the rectangular current matrix two decoders are used which is known as thermometric row decoder and thermometric column decoder. The three most significant bits i.e. B7 to B9 are employed at 3:8 column decoder and the next two bits i.e. B5 to B9 employed at 2:4 row decoder to produce thermometric codes from a binary signal. Again the row decoder output and column decoder output merged to create a local decoder matrix. Then the desired current output drew from the matrix in association with the current reference circuit and clock pulse. The LSB current cells, i.e. binary-weighted sub-DAC have no requirement of any decoder. So to equalize the time delay, a delay circuit is employed to delay the outputs of the input resistor. Then the desired signal obtained from each of the binary cells

will be summed and added with the output current of unary DAC. The resistive load of $50\ \Omega$ each is connected across the current output to obtain the load voltage. Differential current switches are employed to produce the current outputs and the PMOS transistors of Cascode arrangement are used to construct the current sources. With the help of the current mirror circuit a BGR (band-gap reference) circuits are developed to produce the bias voltage.

Fig. 2: Complete Block Diagram of Suggested DAC

Except for all these there are various digital and analog blocks in this arrangement. The vital digital blocks are local decoder, column and row decoders, input resister, and latch circuit. The vital analog parts in this arrangement contain current switches, current sources, and current reference circuits. All these blocks in details are described below.

2.1 Input Resister

In the suggested segmented DAC a 10-bit input resister is employed to harmonies the digital data at a time in association with an internal clock. To implement this input resister a master-slave D flip-flop of a positive-edge trigger is used. A mux-based latch is used for this purpose which is designed with the help of transmission gates. When the clock is on a rising edge, the slave part processes the output data of the master part and for this period, the master part stops sampling the input. On the other hand when the clock pulse is low, the master part becomes short-circuited and the input flows to the output of the master part. During this time, the slave part becomes ideal and provides the previous values of the clock as output using the feedback technique. So the value of output is the same as the D-input when the clock pulse is in a rising edge, and it shows the previous output value as current output when the clock pulse is in a falling edge. Design of this flip-flop using CMOS, make the design durable.

2.2 Column and Row Decoder

In the suggested DAC the five MSB bits are used for binary to thermometric conversion. As it is a 5-bit unary conversion the total no of the current cell is 2^5-1 i.e. 31 numbers. So this can be implemented by using either 1-dimensional or 2-dimensional thermometric decoder. It is batter to use a 2-dimensional technique instead of 1-dimensional, because a 2-dimensional decoder reduces the complexity of the decoder. So to arrange a 4×8 array matrix the first 3 MSBs are used for column conversion and the 2 MSBs are used for row conversion [15]. The decoders are designed precisely to perform low power dissipation and high speed. The logic for this conversion can be decided using K-map for each of the

individual outputs. The relation between binary code and thermometric code is shown in table no 1 for better understanding.

Table 1: Binary to Thermometric 3-bit code Conversion

Binary Code B ₂ B ₁ B ₀	Thermometric Code T ₇ T ₆ T ₅ T ₄ T ₃ T ₂ T ₁ T ₀
000	0000000
001	0000001
010	0000011
011	0000111
100	0001111
101	0011111
110	0111111
111	1111111

The constant outputs can be drawn from V_{DD} and GND by using a buffer for column and row decoder respectively. A schematic representation of the 3:8 Column and 2:4 Row Decoder is shown in Fig. 3(a) and Fig 3(b) respectively.

Fig.3: Representation of Column and Row Decoder

2.3 MSB Current Matrix or Unary Cell

In a local decoder matrix, row and column decoder outputs are again merged to develop the input signals for the latch, which creates the final control signals to regulate the current switches. In this architecture, there are 31 number of unary current cells along with one dummy cell to complete the rectangular matrix. The local decoder MSB matrix can be represented by an AND-OR logic function of the row and column output along with the final latch circuit. This representation is shown in Fig 4.

Fig.4: Representation of Local Decoder matrix

A. Dummy Cell

The name itself gives a basic idea about the cell. This is the same as the other unary cells, but the inputs given to it should be connected to the ground. It is the extreme last cell that is present only to complete the rectangular matrix, but it does not affect the output. The place and concept of a dummy cell for a 4×4 matrix is given in Fig. 5. The blank cells represent the active unary current cells except that dummy one.

	C1	C2	C3	C4
R1				
R2				
R3				
R4				Dummy Cell

Fig.5: Dummy cell in Unary current matrix

2.4 Delay circuit designed by Latch

A final re-timing latch is placed in between the inputs from the thermometric decoder and the differential current switches. The PMOS drivers are used in the architecture of latch because the differential current switches are designed by only a PMOS transistor [18]. If both switches are getting off in any transition for a short span of time, the common source terminal of the differential switches will be a boost to V_{DD} supply and for the next transition the junction capacitance force to get discharge to operate normally. In Fig 6 the design of the latch circuit is given.

Fig.6: Representation of Latch circuit

In the latch circuit, the gates formed by transistors regulated by the digital signals. When the clock is high both the gates become transparent and signal pass into the circuit [12]. The cross-coupled inverters create a feedback loop, which holds the digital value. Again a couple of inverters are kept at either part of the latch stage to step-up the signal inside the circuit. That means when the clock is high the circuit shows the D-input as output and when the clock is low, the circuit shows the previous data.

2.5 Clock Buffer Circuit

To minimize the effect of glitches the control signals regulating the PMOSs of the current switches need to be adjusted. By increasing the logic low voltage the voltage swing can be reduced and by delaying a short span of time, the rise time of one of the differential signals can be changed. This method is acceptable if the rise times of the control signals are identical. The switch transistor size for LSB current source i.e. $5\mu\text{A}$ is fixed on $2\mu\text{m}\times 180\text{nm}$. For $10\mu\text{A}$ current source the finger number of the PMOS switch is increased to two, for $10\mu\text{A}$ current source finger should be increased to four and so on. The finger numbers along with the size of the switches for the generation of $40\mu\text{A}$ current is shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Differential current switches for 40 μA current source

2.6 Band-gap Current Reference Circuit

A digital to analog converter requires a band-gap current reference circuit extensively [7]. The current flow should be independent to increase or decrease in temperature. Again this current gets divided into two parts and fed to the differential current switches with the help of a bias circuit which is given in the next section. The generations of temperature-independent current and bias circuits are described below.

Fig.8: Temperature independent Current Reference Circuit using Current Mirror

Reference voltage and current that shows a negligible dependence on increasing and decreasing of temperature is highly essential for many of the commonly used analog circuits. Though most of the process parameters vary in accordance with temperature, but the can behave temperature-independent if the reference source is independent of temperature. But to produce a source independent of temperature with better quality is not so easy. It is decided that if two sources of opposite polarity are added with proper weightage, then the resultant source might be independent of temperature [12, 16, and 17]. That means if $V1$ and $V2$ are opposite with variation of temperature and $\alpha_1 \frac{\partial V1}{\partial T} + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial V2}{\partial T} = 0$, then the reference voltage independent of temperature can be obtained from

$$V_{REF} = \alpha_1 V1 + \alpha_2 V2 \quad (1)$$

The voltage reference circuit can be designed by using the current mirror technique. After getting the constant voltage, the constant current independent of temperature can be obtained from the node by using resistors parallel to the bipolar transistors. The schematic of a current reference circuit is shown in Fig. 8. The constant current should be obtained in a good shape within a very negligible variation, thus can be treated as constant.

2.7 Current Sources

The current sources are the vital sub-circuit of the current steering DAC. During the design of the current sources, special care should be taken, because it causes a mismatch of transistors, an increase of chip area, output impedance, and power consumption. In current steering DAC matching of the current sources is responsible for INL determination. The increasing size of the transistors helps to match the current cells, but they capture large areas and reduce the performance of the converter at high frequency

[9]. So it is better to design the current sources with ideal size. By use of Pelgrom Model the minimum width and length of the MOSFET can be determined. The minimum area of the transistor can be determined from Equation (2).

$$(W \times L)_{min} = \frac{4A_{vt}^2}{\frac{(V_{gs}-V_t)^2 + A_{\beta}^2}{2 \times \sigma^2(I)}} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\sigma^2(I)}{I^2} \leq \frac{1}{2C\sqrt{2\pi}} \quad (3)$$

Where A_{vt} is the threshold voltage mismatch parameter, A_{β} is the current factor mismatch parameter, V_{gs} is the gate to source voltage of transistors, V_t is the threshold voltage and $\sigma^2(I)/I^2$ is the relative standard deviation of the current sources. To maintain the $INL \leq 0.5$ LSB, the $\sigma^2(I)/I^2$ should be as given in Eq. 3, where $C = \text{Inv-norm}(.5 \pm \frac{\text{yield}}{2})$ and n represents the resolution of the DAC. After calculation, the size of the driver transistor is chosen for LSB current of $5\mu\text{A}$ is $2\mu\text{m} \times 1.5\mu\text{m}$. Similarly, the size of the Cascode transistor is $2\mu\text{m} \times 0.5\mu\text{m}$ for the $5\mu\text{A}$ current. For $10\mu\text{A}$ and $20\mu\text{A}$ current the finger number should be increased to 2 and 4 respectively and so on for other desired current sources. The bias circuit which produces two differential voltages by using the constant current reference voltage is given in Fig. 9. In this circuit the size of M_{N1} and M_{N3} are equal with M_{N2} and M_{N4} respectively. The use of a voltage bias circuit reduces the voltage drop due to the long channel [13].

Fig.9: Voltage Bias Circuit

3. SIMULATION RESULT

The entire simulations have been performed in the latest version of cadence virtuoso simulation software. The suggested DAC output can be seen in Fig.10 which is a clearly a ramp output containing some glitches. Again the extended version of this out can give a clear vision in glitches observation which is given in Fig.11.

Fig. 10: Ramp output from 0 to full-scale using Cadence Virtuoso IC-615 Simulation Software

Fig. 11: Extended Ramp output with mid-code glitch using Cadence Virtuoso IC-615 Simulation Software

This 10-bit segmented DAC achieves an optimum INL value of 0.317 LSB and optimum DNL value of 0.184 LSB as shown in fig. 12 and fig. 13 respectively. The mismatch effect can be analyzed by using Monte Carlo-Mismatch analysis and for this analysis; the cadence ADE XL tool of the same virtuoso version is needed.

Fig.12. Simulated INL plot of the DAC using Cadence Virtuoso IC-615 Simulation Software

Fig.13. Simulated DNL plot of the DAC using Cadence Virtuoso IC-615 Simulation Software

The below-given equation (4) can be used for calculation of the SFDR (Spurious Free Dynamic Range) of the output signal. Here N is the resolution of the DAC. It is suggested to have a low SFDR for better linearity [14]. Table 2 represents the outlines of the simulation results of the suggested 10-bit DAC.

$$SFDR \approx 20 \log \left(\frac{2^N}{INL_{max}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Table 2: Simulation results' outlines of the suggested DAC

Measuring Parameters	Value
Sampling Rate	500 MSPS

Power Supply	1.8 V
Resolution	10-bit
Process	0.18 μm CMOS
INL (LSB)	0.317 LSB
DNL (LSB)	0.184 LSB
Power Dissipation	7.56 mW
SFDR	56.12 dB

4. LIMITATIONS

Though the suggested DAC can be very much helpful for improvements in linearity, but still, some limitations are pre-attached and some occurred during its implementation. Some notable limitations can be stated below.

- I. The larger current sources may cause the parasitic increment which can reduce the performance of DAC.
- II. The performance of DAC is sensitive to high frequency; hence it can give an unexpected result.
- III. The design is limited to a few ranges of inputs.
- IV. The outputs contain some glitches due to external noises which causes losses in information.

5. CONCLUSION

Implementation of this DAC has been carried out in cadence virtuoso IC-615 simulation software. It requires a very less amount of supply voltage of value 1.8 V only for initial operation. The DAC is a high-bandwidth digital-to-analog converter that is able to process the information at a rate of five hundred samples per second. It's a 10-bit high-resolution DAC. The DAC can perform wireless transmission. A 5-metal CMOS process is adopted for designing of this DAC. This 5-metal CMOS process can be done in the advanced 180 nm technology. The simulation result gives an integral non-linearity (INL) and differential non-linearity (DNL) value of 0.0317 LSB & 0.0184 LSB respectively. It is the maximum value of INL and DNL. The maximum SFDR value of this suggested DAC is 56.12 dB. Again a maximum power dissipation of 7.56 mW is happened at the Nyquist signal frequency with 500 MSPS and at 1.8 voltage supply only.

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